

Knowledge of Farmers towards the Usage of Social Media for Acquiring Agricultural Information

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Social media has become a crucial tool for getting agricultural information, supporting farmers in making informed decisions regarding crop management, market prices, weather forecasts, and government schemes. This study intends to analyse the knowledge levels of farmers regarding the employment of social media for accessing agricultural information in the chosen districts of Haryana. Using an exploratory study approach, data were obtained from 120 farmers through a scheduled interview schedule. The data suggest that while platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp, and YouTube are widely recognised and employed, the adoption of agriculture-specific applications like Krishi Network, Krishify, and Krishi Jagran remains low. Statistical study suggests that age, education, subsidiary occupation, annual income, landholding size, social participation, and extension contacts greatly influence farmers' knowledge levels. The study underscores the need for focused digital literacy activities and greater accessibility to agricultural applications to bridge the digital divide and enhance farmers' engagement with social media for agricultural developments.

Keywords: Social media, digital literacy and socio-economic factors

The usage of social media has become a fundamental component of existence for many people worldwide. In 2019, 2.95 billion individuals engaged with social media regularly on a global scale. This is projected to exceed 3.43 billion by 2023 (Statistica, 2020). Digital communication technologies, including the Internet, social media, and mobile applications, have become integral to the daily lives of billions globally (Dwivedi et al., 2021). India is one of the "fastest growing fintech markets" globally, distinguished as a leader in digitalization with increasing telecom and internet penetration. (RBI, 2021).

As of April 2022, India possessed the second-largest telecom client base (1,167.82 million) and the second-highest number of Internet users (788.77 million) globally (IBEF, 2022). By 2025, the global number of internet users is projected to reach 900 million, marking a substantial increase from the current statistic (IMAI, 2023). Social media use is now an essential feature of life for a vast number of people globally. In 2019, 2.95 billion individuals engaged with social media regularly across the globe. This is projected to exceed 3.43 billion by 2023 (Statistica, 2020). The expansion of social media and digitization are vital in many spheres of society. They drive businesses to adjust their marketing techniques in

response to changing consumer behavior, which fosters innovation and competitiveness. Tiago and Veríssimo (2014) underline how crucial it is for organizations to embrace digital marketing to boost consumer co-creation and communication. Social media gives a revolutionary possibility for agriculture, particularly in tackling the issues encountered by farmers. The interplay between policy measures, such as "greening" programs, and economic pressures underscores the need for innovative solutions (House of Commons, 2011). However, concerns regarding the digital divide between rural and urban areas persist, aggravating pre-existing disadvantages. Despite these limitations, social media allows farmers a platform for communication, information collecting, and successful produce marketing (Morris & James, 2017). Farmers can boost trustworthiness, communicate with customers, and transfer knowledge by leveraging social media platforms like Facebook and WhatsApp (Balkrishna et al., 2017). The use of social media makes communication more effective, which could revolutionize conventional agricultural approaches (Lathiya et al., 2015). In addition, social media integration in agriculture addresses farmers' information expectations, helping them to make intelligent decisions and raising agricultural productivity (Aldosari et al., 2019). In general, social media encourages entrepreneurship and innovation in agriculture by connecting farmers with markets and supporting long-term, stable growth in the sector. Recent empirical research shows that social media acts as an informal extension system, particularly in locations where established agricultural extension services are insufficient or overstretched (Chapman & Slaymaker, 2017). Through peer-to-peer learning and experiential knowledge sharing, farmers increasingly rely on digital platforms to acquire timely, localized, and cost-effective agricultural information (Klerkx, Jakku, & Labarthe, 2019). Moreover, social media-mediated networks boost social capital among farmers, enhancing collective problem-solving, innovation dissemination, and resilience in rural livelihoods (Strong, Ganpat, & Harder, 2014). In developing agrarian contexts such as India, these digital interactions are crucial for overcoming information asymmetries and

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empowering farmers in decision-making processes (Mittal & Mehar, 2016).

The Haryana government is urging farmers to use social media for information sharing. The “kisan Mitra Mobile App” was introduced by the Haryana agriculture department. This app allows farmers access wide range of Information and services, including crop advice, market price, weather updates and government initiatives. It allows farmers to communicate with agriculture specialist and fellow farmers through social media capabilities within the app (Anonymous, 2020). These studies emphasize the increased use of social media by farmers to communicate with farming communities, share farming-related information, and improve agricultural sustainability and production. Examples of these platforms include Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, WhatsApp, Twitter, and Facebook. (Singh & Verma, 2023).

Objectives of the Study

- To assess the knowledge of farmers regarding usage of Social Media
- To know the knowledge level of respondents
- To delineate the socio-economic factors associated with the knowledge level

Method

Participants

The exploratory research design was employed to measure the knowledge level of farmer related use of social media for Acquiring Agricultural information. The study was conducted out in two randomly selected districts of Haryana, with one block chosen from each district. Two villages were randomly picked from each block to ensure broad representation. A total of 120 respondents (60 from each district) were selected for the study.

Measure

To collect data, a semi- organized and pre-tested interview schedule was established, concentrating on testing respondents' knowledge of different social media platform used for agricultural purposes (e.g., Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube, etc.).

Procedure

The knowledge levels were evaluated by asking the respondents to reply to different statements about social media usage for agricultural information. Responses were recorded and grouped into three knowledge levels: low, medium, and high. These were assigned scores based on a preset classification scheme.

Statistical Analysis

The acquired data were analysed using frequency, percentage, and

chi-square (χ^2) testes to identify the distribution of knowledge levels among the respondents and assess the association between socio-economic variables and knowledge levels. Statistical analysis was performed using MS Eexcel and the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software.

Results

Table 1 shows that the majority, 91.66 per cent of respondents reported that Facebook is a social media app, followed by a substantial majority, 95.83 per cent, who knew how to log into Facebook, indicating high proficiency in accessing the platform, whereas 4.16 per cent of respondents were not able to start Facebook. WhatsApp was widely recognized as a messaging app among farmers, with the majority of respondents, 96.67 per cent, followed by 86.67 per cent of respondents, acknowledged that WhatsApp provides information about agriculture. On the other hand, 28.33 per cent of participants who did not consider WhatsApp a helpful tool for solving problems, followed by only 21.67 per cent of respondents were not connected to other farmers through WhatsApp.

YouTube was very popular among respondents and was assumed to be easy to use by the majority of respondents 87.50 per cent followed by a majority 96.67 per cent of respondents who acknowledged YouTube as a visual social media platform. In contrast, 12.50 per cent reported being able to create and upload videos on YouTube, indicating a significant gap in content creation skills. Telegram was not as popular as YouTube, 65 per cent did not recognize it as a messaging app. It was seen that 66.67 per cent of the respondents were not connected with other farmers through Telegram. However, only 35.83 per cent recognized telegram usage for acquiring agricultural information.

Results depict that more than half of respondents 65 per cent did not identify Twitter as a social media app. In contras only one fourth of respondents were able to log in, followed by a similar percentage was able to tweet. Krishi Network is a digital platform for providing agricultural-based information in contradiction it was not recognize as a mobile application by the majority 66.67 per cent of respondents followed by, a majority 70.83 per cent of respondents were not operating the Krishi Network app, while only 31.67 per cent of participants were connected with expert advice through the Krishi Network app indicating a need for better user engagement and training. For Krishify, half of the respondents 60 per cent did not acknowledge it as an agriculture-centric application. Meanwhile, 66.67 per cent did not know that it was a free service and a similar percentage 66.67 per cent of respondents were not registered to the app, indicating potential barriers to registration.

Table 1

Knowledge of the Respondents towards the Usage of Social Media (n=120)

Statements	Yes	No
Facebook is a social media app	110 (91.67)	10 (08.33)
Knowing how to log into Facebook	115 (95.83)	05 (04.17)
Able to know the number of friends on Facebook	74 (61.67)	46 (38.33)
Being able to post queries/videos/pictures on Facebook	50 (41.67)	70 (58.33)
Checking the Facebook friend list	70 (58.33)	50 (41.67)
Knowledge Statements regarding WhatsApp		

WhatsApp is a messaging app	116 (96.67)	04 (03.33)
Provides information about agriculture	104 (86.67)	16 (13.33)
Used for updating the status	88 (73.33)	32 (26.67)
Being connected with other farmers through WhatsApp	94 (78.33)	26 (21.67)
WhatsApp is a helpful tool to solve problems	86 (71.67)	34 (28.33)
Knowledge Statements regarding YouTube		
YouTube is easy to use	105 (87.50)	15 (12.50)
YouTube is a visual social media platform	116 (96.67)	04 (03.33)
Creating and uploading videos on YouTube	15 (12.50)	105 (87.50)
Knowing about agriculture-related YouTube channels	76 (63.33)	44 (36.67)
Knowledge Statements regarding Telegram		
Telegram is a messaging app	42 (35.00)	78 (65.00)
Provides different educational channels	44 (36.67)	76 (63.33)
Utilizing Telegram for acquiring agricultural information	43 (35.83)	77 (64.17)
Being connected with other farmers through Telegram	40 (33.33)	80 (66.67)
Telegram is a helpful tool to address problems	46 (38.33)	74 (61.67)
Knowledge Statements regarding Twitter		
Twitter is a social media app	42 (35.00)	78 (65.00)
Twitter is easy to log in	36 (30.00)	84 (70.00)
Knowing how to tweet on Twitter	36 (30.00)	84 (70.00)
Liking to communicate through Twitter	38 (31.67)	82 (68.33)
Sharing news, links, and pictures on Twitter	40 (33.33)	80 (66.67)
Knowledge Statements regarding Krishi Network		
Krishi Network is a mobile application	40 (33.33)	80 (66.67)
Installing the Krishi Network app on a smartphone	37 (30.83)	83 (69.17)
Operating the Krishi Network app	35 (29.17)	85 (70.83)
The Krishi Network app is easy to use	38 (31.67)	82 (68.33)
Connecting with expert advice through the Krishi Network app	34 (28.33)	86 (71.67)
Knowledge Statements regarding Krishify		
Krishify ia agriculture centric application	48 (40.00)	72 (60.00)
Having the Krishify app on a mobile device	40 (33.33)	80 (66.67)
Krishify is a free service	42 (35.00)	78 (65.00)
Being registered with Krishify	40 (33.33)	80 (66.67)
Krishify helps to solve agricultural problems	42 (35.00)	78 (65.00)
Knowledge Statements regarding Krishi Jagran		
Krishi Jagran is a social media platform especially for farming community	42 (35.00)	78 (65.00)
Browsing updated news on Krishi Jagran	40 (33.33)	80 (66.67)
Using Krishi Jagran as a learning center	36 (30.00)	84 (70.00)
Receiving news alerts via notifications from Krishi Jagran	40 (33.33)	80 (66.67)
Using the Krishi Jagran app for acquiring information	36 (30.00)	84 (70.00)

Note. *Multiple Responses

Lastly, for Krishi Jagran, a large percentage 65 per cent of participants did not identify it as a social media platform. Whereas only one-fourth of the respondents 30 per cent were observed to use Krishi Jagran as a learning centre, while more than half 70 per cent of the responses are contradictory, indicating limited use of this feature and thus did not browse information from it. This interpretation shows the respondents' familiarity and usage patterns of major social media platforms, as well as the regions where utilization is strong and there is scope for development.

Figure in the Parenthesis Denotes the Percentage

Table 2 illustrates the level of knowledge among respondents. One-third of the respondents had a low level of knowledge, followed by 25 per cent who had a medium level of knowledge. In contrast, 35 per cent of the respondents demonstrated a high level of knowledge.

Table 2

Level of Knowledge of the Respondents towards the Usage of Social (n=120)

Level of knowledge	Frequency	Percentage
Low (40-52)	48	40.00
Medium (53-65)	30	25.00
High (66-80)	42	35.00

Relationship between Socio-economic Variables and Knowledge of Farmers towards Social Media

Table 3 presents the relationship between various socio-economic variables and the level of knowledge towards the usage of Social Media for Acquiring Agricultural Information. Results revealed that age, education, subsidiary occupation, annual income, land, social

participation, extension contacts, type of media, Means of communication and socio-economic status were significantly associated with the level of knowledge among respondents. Age was found to be significant at a chi value of 13.04*, indicating that knowledge about social media increased with age. In contrast, education was highly significant at a chi value of 18.44**, indicating that a higher level of education was positively associated with an increase in knowledge. Meanwhile, marital status and caste of the respondent were not significant with for knowledge level.

Subsidiary occupation was found to be significant with chi-value 11.18*, revealing that those with more than one occupation had higher levels of knowledge. Annual income was highly significant at a chi value of 20.20**, with a direct association between income and knowledge level. Almost one-third of the respondents with an annual income above 3,00,001 had a high level of knowledge. The type of

family and size of family were found to be non-significant. With chi value 02.44 married status of respondents was not to be found significant with the knowledge level. 50 per cent of respondents who possess land size between 5 to 10 acres had a high level of knowledge with an overall chi-value of 16.63*. Social participation of respondents, suggesting a relationship with knowledge level showed chi value 11.93*. Type of media used by the respondents was also found to be significant 11.65* in determining the level of knowledge. Extension contacts were significant at a chi value of 09.63*, indicating that they were positively related to knowledge level. Risk regarding social media was non-significant with knowledge level finally, socioeconomic status was highly significant, with 46 per cent of respondents with high socioeconomic status having a higher level of knowledge at a chi value 14.98**.

Table 3

Association between Socio-economic Variables and Level of Knowledge towards Usage of Social Media (n=120)

Socio-economic Variables	Level of knowledge			
	Low	Medium	High	Total
Age				
(< 39 years)	04(14.81)	07(25.93)	16(59.26)	27(22.50)
(Between 39 - 50 years)	31(44.29)	17(24.28)	22(31.43)	70(58.33)
(> 50 years)	13(56.52)	06(26.09)	04(17.39)	23(19.17)
Total	48(40.00)	30(25.00)	42(35.00)	120(100)
χ^2 Cal =13.04*				
Education				
Illiterate	07(53.85)	05(38.46)	01(7.69)	13(10.83)
Primary - Middle	21(51.22)	09(21.95)	11(26.83)	41(34.17)
Secondary	19(40.43)	11(23.40)	17(36.17)	47(39.17)
Graduate and above	01(05.26)	05(26.32)	13(68.42)	19(15.83)
χ^2 Cal =18.44**				
Caste				
General category	22(37.29)	17(28.81)	20(33.90)	59(49.17)
Backward class	19(44.19)	07(16.28)	17(39.53)	43(35.83)
Scheduled caste	07(38.89)	06(33.33)	05(27.78)	18(15.00)
χ^2 Cal =03.00				
Subsidiary Occupation				
Nil	27(54.00)	12(24.00)	11(22.00)	50(41.67)
Service	08(26.67)	06(20.00)	16(53.33)	30(25.00)
Small scale enterprise	13(32.05)	12(30.00)	15(37.05)	40(33.33)
χ^2 Cal =10.43*				
Annual Income (RS)				
Up to 1,50,000	17(62.96)	07(25.93)	03(11.11)	27(22.50)
Between 1,50,001-3,00,000	08(17.78)	16(35.56)	21(46.66)	45(37.50)
Above 3,00,001	23(47.92)	07(14.58)	18(37.50)	48(40.00)
χ^2 Cal =20.20**				
Type of family				
Nuclear	38(36.89)	27(26.22)	38(36.89)	103(85.83)
Joint	10(58.82)	03(17.65)	04(23.53)	17(14.17)
χ^2 Cal =02.93				
Size of family				
Up to 4 members	34(39.53)	20(23.26)	32(37.21)	86(71.67)
Between 5-7 members	04(26.67)	07(46.66)	04(26.67)	15(12.50)
Above 7 members	10(52.63)	03(15.79)	06(31.58)	19(15.83)
χ^2 Cal =05.48				

Marital status				
Married	44(40.00)	27(24.55)	39(35.45)	110(91.67)
Unmarried	04(40.00)	03(30.00)	03(30.00)	10(88.33)
χ^2 Cal =00.18				
Landholding				
Marginal (Less than 2.5 acres)	05(50.00)	04(40.00)	01(10.00)	10(88.33)
Small (between 2.5-5 acres)	14(58.33)	06(25.00)	04(16.67)	24(20.00)
Semi-medium (between 5-10 acres)	11(22.00)	14(28.00)	25(50.00)	50(41.67)
Medium (Above 10- 25 acres)	18(50.00)	06(16.67)	12(33.33)	36(30.00)
χ^2 Cal =16.63*				
Social participation				
Nil	09(34.62)	12(46.15)	05(19.23)	26(21.67)
Member of one organization	17(53.13)	06(18.74)	09(28.13)	32(26.66)
Member of more than one organization	22(35.48)	12(19.35)	28(45.17)	62(51.67)
χ^2 Cal =11.93*				
Type of media				
Low (8-12)	16(57.14)	08(28.57)	04(14.29)	28(23.33)
Medium (13-18)	17(47.22)	08(22.22)	11(30.56)	36(30.00)
High (19-24)	15(26.79)	14(25.00)	27(48.21)	56(46.67)
χ^2 Cal =11.65*				
Extension contacts				
Low (5-8)	06(19.35)	11(35.48)	14(45.17)	31(25.83)
Medium (9-12)	34(49.28)	16(23.19)	19(27.53)	69(57.50)
High (13-15)	08(40.00)	03(15.00)	09(45.00)	20(16.67)
χ^2 Cal = 09.63*				
Means of communication				
Low (15-25)	08(32.00)	08(32.00)	09(36.00)	25(20.83)
Medium (26-35)	19(67.86)	04(14.28)	05(17.86)	28(23.34)
High (36-45)	21(31.34)	18(26.87)	28(41.79)	67(55.83)
χ^2 Cal =12.18*				
Risk orientation				
Low (5-8)	18(39.13)	12(26.09)	16(34.78)	46(38.33)
Medium (9-12)	13(43.33)	05(16.67)	12(40.00)	30(25.00)
High (13-15)	17(38.63)	13(29.55)	14(31.82)	44(36.67)
χ^2 Cal =01.63				
Socio-economic status				
Low (6-9)	07(53.85)	05(38.46)	01(07.69)	13(09.92)
Medium (10-13)	32(47.06)	18(26.47)	18(26.47)	68(51.91)
High (14-16)	09(18.00)	18(36.00)	23(46.00)	50(38.17)
χ^2 Cal =14.98**				

Note. Figures in parenthesis denote per cent, *Significant at 5 per cent, **Highly Significant at 1 per cent

Discussion

The study revealed that; one-third of the respondents had a low level of knowledge, followed by 35 per cent who had a high level of knowledge. In contrast, 25 per cent of the respondents demonstrated a medium level of knowledge. Results are in line with the study of Pattabhi et al. (2023) conducted in Telangana state with majority 72.50 per cent of the respondents' level of knowledge was found to be low. In contradiction, Jena et al. (2024) findings depicted that 90 per cent of the farmers had medium level of social media access.

The results of the research show an association between respondents' knowledge level and age, education, subsidiary occupation, annual income, land holding, social participation, type of media, extension contacts, means of communication, and socioeconomic status. Specifically, income, socioeconomic status,

and education were found to be highly significant, indicating that higher levels of education. The findings were in line with (Raghuprasad et al., 2013), who discovered in their study "An analysis of farmers' knowledge level on utilization of ICT tools for farm communication" that education, land holding, and annual income had a positive and significant relationship with farmers' knowledge level on ICT utilization, whereas family type and mass media exposure had no significant relationship with farmers' knowledge level on ICT utilization.

Pattabhi et al. (2023) had also reached a similar conclusion, stating that there is a positive and significant difference between farmers' knowledge of social media and independent variables such as digital literacy, farm size, the social media network, social media usage, information processing, mode of access and preference, willingness to accept information and social media participation. In

opposition, it may be inferred that there is no substantial association between age, farming experience, and farmers' understanding of social media. This association between age and knowledge could be explained by middle-aged people's cumulative experience or their diminished ability to retain information as they age. The factor of agricultural knowledge may be related to enhance understanding via experience, but also social media usage.

Conclusion

The study concludes that social media plays a crucial role in the dissemination of agricultural information among farmers in Haryana. The majority of farmers are familiar with general social media platforms like Facebook, WhatsApp, and YouTube, which they primarily use for communication and information sharing. However, awareness and utilization of specialized agricultural applications remain limited. The findings suggest that age, education level, subsidiary occupation, income, landholding, and social participation significantly impact farmers' knowledge and usage of social media for agriculture. It is imperative to implement targeted training programs, enhance accessibility to digital tools, and improve the usability of agriculture-specific applications. Bridging the digital divide between urban and rural areas can empower farmers with timely and accurate information, leading to increased productivity and sustainable agricultural practices.

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